

Some Metabolites Extracted from Endophytic Bacteria L-2 Isolated from the Leaves of Pineapple (*Ananas comosus* Merr.)

Nu Yin Aye *

Abstract

Fifteen strains of endophytic microorganisms were screened from leaves of pineapple. Among the isolated strains, two days old culture of Fraction number L-2, L-3, L-4, L-7 and L-11 showed the prominent antibacterial activities against *Bacillus subtilis*, *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* sp. These isolated microorganisms were tested for their hydrolytic activity and antimicrobial activity. Strain No. L-2 having high potential in both activities was selected for the screening of metabolites. Medium 1 in which 1% glucose was added into nutrient broth was utilized as the basal fermentation medium. After 2 days, fermented broth was extracted *n*-butanol to provide metabolite. Butanol layer after been evaporated was examined and found to be presence of amino acids. Therefore qualitative tests for the presence of amino acids were carried out. Thin layer chromatographic analysis using authentic amino acids revealed the presence of eight amino acids in the metabolite extracts from the endophytes. Precipitates obtained from the *n*-butanol extract were subjected to phytochemical tests and TLC analyses. The precipitate was insoluble in organic solvents but soluble in boiling water. Fourier Transforms Infra-Red (FTIR) analysis was also carried out for this precipitate.

Introduction

Life on Earth would have been impossible without microorganism in nature. There are numerous varieties which are living on earth and are deeply involved with human life (Harayama and Isono, 2002). Microorganisms have significant functions in ecosystems and are found in all kinds of habitats. Endophytes are defined as microorganisms which inhabit inside of healthy plant tissue and are now considered as ubiquitous symbionts of plants from their surprisingly common detection from many plant species (Petrini, 1986).

They stimulate the production of secondary metabolites with a diverse range to produce enormous variety of strange and wonderful compound. Microorganisms living within plant tissues for all or part of their life cycle without causing any visible symptoms of their presence are defined as endophytes. The systematic investigation reveals that traditional medicinal are rich and reliable source of novel endophytic fungi and bacteria. (Huang *et al.*, 2007). Many recent studies have revealed the ubiquity of these with an estimate of at least 1 million species of endophytic bacteria residing in plants (Dreyfuss and Chapela, 1994). Several bacterial endophytes have been shown to support plant growth and increase nutrient uptake by providing phytohormones (Jacobson *et al.*, 1994), low molecular weight compounds (Frommel *et al.*, 1991), enzymes (Glick *et al.*, 1998), antimicrobial substances like antibiotics (Bangera and Thomashow, 1996) and siderophores (Sullivan and Gara, 1992).

In the present work, all endophytic bacteria are screened from the mature healthy plant of pineapple leaves, and culture on five different selected media. All the isolated endophytic organisms are applied in the tests of enzymatic activity. Some of the morphological, cultural and biochemical characteristics are also investigated. Besides, the presence of antimicrobial activities of all isolated strains are also studied by using six test organisms and the formation of eight amino acids and gummy substance in the fermented broth using isolated L-2 strain was reviewed.

* Dr., Assistant Lecturer, Department of Botany, Dagon University

Aims and Objectives

- To find out new and useful endophytic bacteria from healthy plant parts of pineapple leaves
- To discover the hydrolytic potential on carbohydrate, protein and lipid
- To investigate some antibacterial activity by using six test organisms
- To study some metabolites in the fermented medium by isolated endophytes

Materials and Methods

Collection of Sample

Leaves of pineapple (*Ananas comosus* Merr; Fam. Bromeliaceae) were collected from plantation site of Lein-mo-chan Village, Taikkyi Township, Yangon Region. Taikkyi Township located in northern district of Yangon Region between 17° 25' and East 95° 00'. The township located 5 m above sea level.

The collected leaves were washed in running water for ten minutes. Leaves were cut into pieces (1-3 cm), sterilized by soaking in 70% alcohol for three minutes, and rinsed with sterilized distilled water for 5 minutes. Water on the leaves was removed by soaking with sterilized paper. Then, leaves placed on five different selected media plates and incubated for 24 hours.

Preparation of Culture Media

Medium 1		Medium 2	
Peptone	0.5 g	Peptone	0.5 g
NaCl	0.5 g	NaCl	0.5 g
Yeast	0.2 g	Yeast	0.2 g
Beef	0.1 g	Beef	0.1 g
Glucose	1.0 g	Lactose	1.0 g
Agar	2.5 g	Agar	2.5 g
Distilled Water (DW)	100 ml	Distilled Water (DW)	100 ml
pH	7.0 ± 0.2	pH	7.0 ± 0.2
Medium 3		Medium 4 (King's Medium)	
Peptone	0.5 g	Peptone	2.0 g
NaCl	0.5 g	Glycerol	1.0 g
Yeast	0.2 g	K ₂ HPO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	1.0 g
Beef	0.1 g	MgCl ₂ · 7H ₂ O	0.1 g
Sucrose	1.0 g	Agar	2.5 g
Agar	2.5 g	Distilled Water (DW)	100 ml
Distilled Water (DW)	100 ml	pH	7.0±0.2
pH	7.0 ± 0.2		
Medium 5 (Nutrient Agar)			
	Peptone	0.5 g	
	NaCl	0.5 g	
	Yeast	0.2 g	
	Meat	0.1 g	
	Agar	2.5 g	
	Distilled Water (DW)	100 ml	
	pH	7.0 ± 0.2	

Antibiotic Nystatin (Ca. 0.001%) was added to the culture media to suppress the growth of fungi. The pure endophytic bacterial strains were photographed and preserved at room temperature.

Figure 1. Flow sheet for isolation of the endophytic bacteria

Isolation of Pure Culture from Plates

About 100 ml of five different media were separately distributed into test tubes. The test tubes were plugged with cotton wool and sterilized by autoclaving at 15 pounds pressure per square inch for 15 minutes at 121°C. The sterilized media were cooled down. The separate colonies appear and the different types of bacterial colonies were cultured in test tubes. The slant media were repeatedly sub-cultured to obtain pure cultures (Atlas, 1993).

The Study of Morphological Characteristics

Gram Staining

A drop of sterile distilled water was placed on clean grease-free slide and a small loop of isolated bacteria was smeared on the slide and allows it to dry. The smear was fixed by passing the dried slide rapidly over a flame 3 or 4 times. The slide was covered with crystal violet stain and allowed it to act for 30-60 seconds. Then, the slide was rinsed with distilled water for a few seconds. The slide was covered with fresh iodine solution and allowed it to act for about 30-60 seconds. Alcohol was added drop by drop until no more colour flowed out from the smear. For a thin smear, 10-20 seconds might be enough for complete decolourization of gram negative bacteria. As a counter stain, the smear was covered with safranin for 20-30 seconds and washed with distilled water. Then, the slide was air dried. The strained slide was examined under the oil immersion objective of the microscope (Atlas, 1993).

Motility

Motility was checked by hanging drop preparation of young culture and examined them under the microscope (Cruickshank *et al.*, 1968).

Catalase Test

Few drops of 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution were placed onto each slide culture and watched for immediate signs of bubbling, which represented positive test; absence of bubbles indicated a negative test (Salle, 1948).

Oxygen Requirement (Aerobic / Anaerobic)

Different test-tubes of slant cultures and broth cultures are prepared and then one is inoculated at room temperature. Another culture is kept in the anaerobic tin can. Different culture at agar test tubes is prepared as usual and the isolated strains are made as stab-culture and incubated at room temperature. The patterns of growth are checked daily and the oxygen requirement of the isolated strain was recorded (Prescott, 2002).

Determination of Enzymatic Activity

(a) Amylolytic Activity

Rice, sticky rice, maize, wheat powder were utilized for source of starch powder. Starch agar (peptone 0.5 g, yeast 0.5 g, agar 2.5 g, above each starch powder 1%, distilled water 100 ml, pH 7.0 ± 0.2) was incubated with isolated strains for 24 hours. Then, dilute iodine solution was flooded on the surface of starch agar checked visually. Hydrolysis of starch was indicated by clear zones around the growth of bacteria and recorded as positive reaction. Unchanged starch gave a blue-black colour (Pelezar and Chan, 1972).

(b) Proteolytic Activity

(1) Casein Hydrolysis

Hydrolysis of casein (milk protein) was tested according to the procedure described by Pelezar and Chan (1972). Milk agar, which contain 10% (v/v) of skim milk in nutrient agar was sterilized at 15 psi and 121°C for 15 minutes and separately poured into petridishes. The sterile milk agar plates were separately inoculated by streaking once across the surface and incubated at 27°C for two days. The formation of visible clear zone on the milk agar plates due to the treatment of 10 % mercuric chloride in 20 % hydrochloric acid (Pelezar and Chan, 1972).

(2) Gelatin Hydrolysis

The composition of medium contains gelatin 1 %, peptone 0.4 g , yeast extract 0.1 g, agar 2.5 g and Distilled water 100 ml at pH 7.0 ± 0.2. The sterilized culture medium was incubated with isolated strain at 30°C for a week. Then, saturated ammonium sulphate solution was poured onto the surface of gelatin agar. Hydrolysis of gelatin was indicated by clear zones around the growth and recorded as positive reaction (Cruickshank, 1968).

(c) Esterase Activity

The medium contains Peptone 1.0 g, NaCl 0.5g, CaCl₂.2H₂O 0.01 g, agar 2.5 g and Distilled water 100 ml at pH 7.4. To sterilized culture media, previously sterilized Tween 80 was added in a final concentration of 1% (v/v). This medium was inoculated with the isolated strains and the presence of halos was checked daily (Prescott, 2002).

(d) Lipase Activity

The used of medium was containing Peptone 1.0 g, NaCl 0.5 g, CaCl₂.2H₂O 0.01 g, agar 2.5 g and Distilled water 100 ml at pH 7.4. To sterilize culture media, previously sterilized Tween 20 was added in a final concentration of 1% (v/v). This medium was inoculated with the isolated strains and the presence of halos observed (Prescott, 2002).

(e) Growth on Potato Plug

Surface-sterilized and potato tubers were cut into 8 mm thick slices and placed each slice on a petridish and then autoclave at 15 psi and 121°C for 15 minutes. The isolated strain was streak-incubated with a loopful of a nutrient agar culture and incubated for 24 hours (Atlas, 1993).

Antimicrobial Activity Test

The study of antibacterial activity was performed by paper disc diffusion method. 25 ml of the boiled nutrient medium was poured into each test tube, plugged with cotton wool and autoclaved at 15 psi and 121°C for 15 minutes. Then the tubes were cooled down to 30-35°C and poured into each sterilized petridish and 0.1 ml of test organisms were also added into the dishes. Similarly, the nutrient broth cultures of isolated strains were prepared as the same method as described above. The six different types of test organisms were also used to prepare the basal petridishes and subjected in the antimicrobial activity test. Paper dishes 4 mm in diameter were soaked with 0.02 ml of 1 to 3 days old culture broths at isolated strains and placed on the basal agar plates and then the petridishes were inverted and incubated for 24 hours at room temperature. Then the size of clear zone around paper disc was measured and recorded as the antibacterial activity against pathogenic test organisms (Prescott, 2002).

Qualitative Test for Amino Acid

There are some qualitative tests to detect the presence of amino acids in an unknown sample (Buzarbarua, 2000). Some of the important tests are mentioned below:

Experiment	Observation	Remarks
1. Ninhydrin Reaction Take 1 ml of filtrate (butanol extract) solution of 1% concentration into a test tube and add 1ml of ninhydrin reagent. N.B. The pH of the solution must be between 4 and 8.	i. Purple colour will be formed. ii. Yellow colour complex formed.	Indicates the presence of all amino acids. Proline and hydroxyproline present.
2. Xanthoproteic reaction Add 1ml of conc. nitric acid to 1ml of the amino acid solution, cool and observe the colour change. Add sufficient 40% NaOH to make the solution strongly alkaline.	Yellow colour develops. Yellow colour turns bright orange with alkali solution.	Indicates the presence of glycine, tyrosine and tryptotan. Do
3. Millon's reaction Add a few drops of the reagent to 1ml of the test solution and heat in boiling water both for 10 minute. After cooling add 5 drops of 1% solution nitrite solution.	Brick red colour appears.	Tryosine and its derivatives are present.
4. Glyoxylic reaction Add 2ml of this solution to 2ml of the test solution. Mix well and then add 2ml of conc. H ₂ SO ₄ down the sides of the tube.	A violet ring appears at the junction of the two layers.	Indicates the presence of the amino acid tryptophan.
5. Ehrlich's test Add 1ml of the Ehtllch's reagent to 1ml of the test solution and observe the colour.	Blue colour appears.	Tryptophan present.

Phytochemical Examination of Crude Extract from the Broth Culture of Isolated L-2

The metabolite in the crude extract of broth (filtrate of L-2) was phytochemically examined according to the methods of Harbone (1984). Qualitative tests included were tests for alkaloids, glycosides, steriods and terpenoids, phenolic compounds, acid/base/neutral, starch and cyanogenic glycosides.

Thin Layer Chromatographic Examination of Filtrate L-2

The purified isolated extract was examined by the application of TLC, using silica gel precoated plates (E. Merck) according to the methods of Stecher (1968) and Harbone (1984) with a slight modification. The solvent system was used *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4:1:1 v/v) and sprayed reagent was 0.3% ninhydrin solution for the presence of eight amino acid.

Physicochemical Examination of Precipitate obtained from L-2 Broth

Precipitate from butanol extract of L-2 Broth was examined for its physicochemical properties according to Steacher (1968) and Buzarbarua (2000). Tests were especially done for carbohydrates such as iodine test, Fehling test, tannic acid test and solubility test.

Thin Layer Chromatographic Examination of Precipitates obtained from L-2 Broth

The precipitate was examined by the application of TLC, using silica gel precoated plates (E.Merck) according to the methods of Stecher (1968) and Harbone (1984) with slight modification. The solvent system used were (I) 65% isopropanol : EtOAc (65:35 v/v) and (II) *n*-butanol : acetone : phosphate buffer pH-5 (40:50:10). Chromatograms were visualized by spraying with anisaldehyde, for the presence of maltose and glucose (Stahl, 1969).

Fourier Transform Infra Red Spectroscopic Analysis (FT-IR)

The IR spectrum of isolated precipitate was recorded on Shimadzu FTIR 8400at the Universities' Research Centre, Yangon.

Results

Screening of Endophytic Bacteria Strains

Table 1. Isolated endophytes from five different culture media

Culture Media	Designated strains
Medium 1	L 1 - 4
Medium 2	L 5 - 6
Medium 3	L 7 - 8
Medium 4	L 9 - 11
Medium 5	L 12 - 15

In this work, altogether fifteen isolated strains were maintained into pure culture and designated as L (1 – 15).

Cultural Characters and Cell Morphology

Figure 2. Cultural characters and cell morphology of isolated endophytic bacteria from pineapple leaves.

Table 2. Morphology of isolated strains

Test	Isolated Strains														
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Cell morphology	R	C	St C	SR	O	O	O	R	C	C	C	R	C	O	O
Gram strain	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+
Catalyse test	+	+	++	++	++	++	+	+	+	+	+	++	++	++	++
Motility	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
Aerobic/Anaerobic	An	An	A	An	An	An	An	A	A	A	A	An	An	An	An

C = coccus R = rod St C = Streptococcus SR = short rod O = Oval
 + = presence - = absence A = Aerobic An = Anaerobic

Table 3. Hydrolysis test of isolated strains

Hydrolysis Test	Isolated Strains															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	
Rice hydrolysis	-	+	++	-	-	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	-	++	++	-
Sticky hydrolysis	-	++	-	-	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++
Maize hydrolysis	+	+	++	+	++	+	++	+	++	-	-	+	-	-	-	
Wheat hydrolysis	-	++	-	++	-	-	+	++	-	++	++	+	++	++	-	
Potato hydrolysis	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	
Casein hydrolysis	-	++	++	-	-	++	-	++	+	++	++	-	-	-	-	
Gelatin hydrolysis	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	++	++	-	-	-	-	-	+	
Esterase activity	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	

+ = hydrolysis ++ = high hydrolysis - = non hydrolysis

Antimicrobial Activity Test

Among all isolated strains from leaves, two days old culture of strains (L- 2, 3, 4, 7 and 11) showed the prominent antibacterial activities against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Estericia coli*.

Figure 3. Test for antimicrobial activity of isolated strains from pineapple leaves

Table 4. Antimicrobial activity of isolated strains from pineapple leaves

Strain No.	<i>Bacillus pumalis</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Candida albican</i>	<i>Estericia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
L-2	-	0.6	-	0.58	0.62	-
L-3	-	0.55	-	0.55	0.55	-
L-4	-	0.6	-	0.57	0.48	-
L-7	-	0.6	-	0.56	0.48	-
L-11	-	0.7	-	0.51	0.6	-

Paper disc = 4 mm

Extraction of Metabolite Compounds from L-2

After 2 days fermentation, the pH of the fermented broth was adjusted to 6.5 - 7.0. The metabolite of L-2 was extracted with the same volume of *n*-butanol using separating funnel for 2-3 times. Repeated extraction of aqueous phase by butanol was conducted until any antimicrobial activity was shown by organic layer when tested by paper disc diffusion assay against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Estericia coli* and *Pseudomonas sp.*

Figure 4. Scheme of Isolated strain from classification to possible Genus level according to Bergey’s Manual.

Table 5. Phytochemical test for filtrate L-2 (*n*-Butanol Extract) according to Harbone (1984)

No	Test	Reagent	Observation	Result
1	Alkaloid Test	1. Dragendroffs Reagent 2. Sodium picrate solution 3. Mayers reagent	no ppt no ppt no ppt	Absent
2	Glycoside Test	10% Lead acetate solution	no ppt	Absent
3	Steroids and Terpenoids	Acetic anhydrite & conc.H ₂ SO ₄ acid	no colour change	Absent
4	Phenolic Compounds	5% Ferric chloride solution	no colour change	Absent
5	Acid/ Base/Neutral	Bromocresol green	no green	Neutral
6	Starch	Iodine solution	no colour change	Absent
7	Cyanogenic glycoside	con. Sulphuric acid + Sodium picrate paper	no colour change	Absent
8	Amino acid Test	Ninhydrin reagent	Violet colour	Present

Phytochemical examinations were done to know the metabolic nature of L-2 filtrate and it provided positive test for amino acid. Other tests gave negative results. Therefore, it is necessary to make TLC analysis. In addition, some qualitative protein tests were done to know the nature of amino acid in Filtrate L-2 by using the method of Buzarbarua (2000). Tests involved were Ninhydrin Reaction, Millon’s Reaction, Ehrlich’s Reaction, Xanthoproteic Reaction and Glyoxylic Reaction.

Solvent system = n-butanol:acetic acid:water (4:1:1 v/v)
 Sprayed reagent = 0.3% ninhydrin solution

L = Lysine; **H** = Histidine; **G** = Glycine;
As/a = Aspartic acid; **G/a** = Glutamic acid;
M = Methionine; **T** = Tyrosine; **Try** = Tryptophan

R_f value: **L**=0.03, **H**=0.06, **G**=0.15, **As/a**=0.24,
G/a=0.34, **T**=0.41, **Try**=0.58

Figure 5. Thin Layer Chromatogram of Filtrate (L-2)

After the TLC examination, it was known that eight amino acids were altogether present in the filtrate of L-2.

Figure 6. FT-IR spectrum of ppt L-2

Table 6. FTIR data of ppt L-2

No	Wave Number (cm ⁻¹)	Function group
1	3419, 3396	OH stretching for hydroxy groups
2	2958, 2926, 2840	CH stretching for CH ₂ and CH ₃ groups
3	1720	C=O stretching vibrations
4	1445	CH ₂ stretching vibration
5	1381	O-H bending vibration
6	1261	C-O-C asymmetric stretching
7	1090	C-O stretching
8	1050	C-O stretching of alcohol

Table 7. Some physico-chemical tests for ppt L-2 according to Steacher (1968) and Buzarbarua (2000)

No.	Experiment	Characterization		Remark	Reference
		Observed	Literature (Starch gum)		
1	Iodine Test	Reddish brown color	Reddish brown colour	Starch absent	Stecher (1968)
2	Fehling Solution Test	No ppt (no color change)	No ppt (no colour change)	No Reducing Sugar	
3	Tannic acid Test	No ppt	No ppt	Starch absent	
4	Solubility Test (a) Cold H ₂ O (b) Boiling H ₂ O (c) EtOH (d) Et ₂ O (e) CHCl ₃	Insoluble Gunny solution In soluble In soluble In soluble	Insoluble Gunny solution In soluble In soluble In soluble	Protein like substance	Buzarbarua (2000)

According to the results it was known that there were no polysaccharide like starch and other monosaccharide such as reducing sugars. But the solubility test results indicated that it may be protein like substance because of insolubility in cold water, soluble in boiling water resulting gummy solution and insolubility in organic solvents.

Examination of Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) for ppt L-2

Figure 7. Chromatogram of ppt L-2

Solvent I = iso-PrOH : EtOAc (65:35, v/v)
 Spray = Anisaldehyde
 R_f : L-2 = 0.15, Maltose = 0.30, Glucose = 0.75

Figure 8. Morphological Character of ppt L-2

Figure 9. Chromatogram of ppt L-2

Solvent II = n-BuOH : (Me)₂CO: PBS pH 5
 (40:50:10 v/v)
 Spray = Anisaldehyde
 R_f : L-2 = 0.30, Maltose = 0.75, Glucose = 1.0

The result at above TLC chromatogram indicated that the precipitate portion of L-2 was neither glucose nor maltose, i.e. there was no monosaccharide or disaccharide. So it is tentatively assumed as oligo or polymeric compound in which amino acid and carbohydrate may be present.

Discussion

Fifteen strains of endophytic bacteria were isolated from the mature and healthy leaves of pineapple were collected from Lein-mo-chan Village, Taik-kyi Township, Yangon Region. Among them, 12 strains were gram positive and 3 strains were gram negative. All isolated strains were examined for presence of enzymatic activities such as amylolytic, proteolytic, esterase and lipase activities. The results, concerning the presence of hydrolytic enzymes in the bacteria in this work was interpreted in accordance with Collin *et al.* (1995). The activity of lipase was found to be absent in all isolated strains. Out of 15 isolated strains from leaves, two days old culture of strains No. 2, 3, 4, 7 and 11 clearly showed the prominent antibacterial activities against *Bacillus subtilis*, *E.coli* and *Pseudomonas sp.* In addition, strain L-2 possesses enzyme and antimicrobial activities. Therefore L-2 was further selected for metabolites study. It is also in agreement with those data reported by Bhore *et al.*, (2010). Identification and biochemical tests of L-2 have been described in Table 2. According to these results, L-2 may be *Staphylococcus*.

The filtrate L-2 was subjected in the physicochemical analyzes as shown in Table 5. The filtrate provides the positive result– there is violet colouration by Ninhydrin reagent; all other tests gave negative results. To confirm the presence at amino acid, the qualitative test for amino acids was conducted as shown in Figure 5. It was well known that to produce amino acids in the large scale, the best source is microorganism applied with favorable fermentation techniques reported by Vijava *et al.*, (2011). Then, TLC analysis of this filtrate by using authentic amino acids with the solvent system of butanol : acetic acid : water (4:1:1 v/v). TLC plate confirmed that eight different types of amino acid were at least present in the filtrate.

The remaining precipitate on the filter paper was used in the qualitative physico-chemical tests in which Iodine test, Fehling's solution, Tannic acid test, Solubility test in different organic solvents and also with water as shown in Table 7. According to Buzarbarua (2000), an extract which was only soluble in hot water may be a gummy substance. The reddish brown color with Iodine test indicated that this substance was not a starch molecule but other polysaccharide. One of the most prominent monosaccharide test of Fehling solution provide negative results. By reviewing above data, the precipitate was found to be a gummy substance, not starch or monosaccharide. Further confirmation was done by Co-TLC analysis using glucose and maltose as standards. Two solvent systems, namely solvent system 1, isopropanol : ethyl acetate (65:35 v/v), and system 2, n-butanol : acetone : phosphate buffer, pH-5 (40:50:10 v/v). It was noted that the maltose was estimated to be R_f value of 0.30, glucose was estimated to be R_f value of 0.75 that of L-2 was estimated to be R_f value of 0.15 for solvent system 1. It was noted that the maltose was estimated to be R_f value of 0.75, glucose was estimated to be R_f value of 1.0 and that of L-2 was estimated to be R_f value of 0.3 for solvent system 2. Fourier Transforms Infra-Red (FTIR) analysis was carried out on this precipitate and indicated that it contained a gummy substance derived from non-starchy component.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it was observed that the eight different kinds of amino acids were detected in the filtrate of butanol fraction. The presence of low molecular weight compounds such as amino acids in the present work is in agreement with Bhore *et.al* (2010). Moreover the gummy substances present in residue of butanol fraction. These metabolites were provided by isolated bacteria from leaves of pineapple.

Acknowledgements

My special thanks are due to Dr. Hla Htay, Rector of Dagon University for his advices and encouragements in this work. I am also grateful to Dr. Than Than Htay, Professor (Head), department of Botany, Dagon University, for her generous help in doing this research. I also thanks to Dr. Myat Myat Moe, Professor, Department of Botany, Dagon University for her advice in this research. I would to express my friend thanks to Dr. Yee Yee Nwe, Assistant Lecturer, Botany, Dagon University, for her help and valuable advices.

References

- Atlas, Ronald M., (1993), "Handbook of Microbiological Media", CRC Press, London
- Bangera M.G. & Thomoshow, L.S., (1996), "Characterization of a genomic locus required for synthesis of the antibiotic 2,4-diacetylphloroglucinal by the biological control agent *Pseudomonas fluorescences* Q.2-87", *MOI plant Microbe Interact*, **9**, 83-90
- Buchanam, R.E. & Gibbon, N.E., (1974), "Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology", 8th Ed., The Willams Wilkins Company, Baltimore
- Buzarbarua, A., (2000), "A Text Book of Practical Plant Chemistry"
- Bhore, S.J., Nithya, R. & Loh, C.Y., (2010), "Screening of endophytic colonizing bacteria for cytokinin-like compounds: Crude cell-free broth of endophytic colonizing bacteria is unsuitable in cucumber cotyledon bioassay", *World J. Agric. Sci.*, **6**, 345-52
- Cruickshank R., Guguid, J.P. & Swain, R.H.A., (1968), "Medical Microbiology", 11th Ed., The English Language Book Soceity and F. and S. Livingstone Ltd., London
- Collins, Patricia, C.H., Lyne, M. & Grange, J.M., (1995), "Collins and Lyne's Microbiological Methods", 7th Ed., Butterworth Heineman, UK, 117
- Dreyfuss, M.M. & Chapela, I.H., (1994), "Potential of fungi in the discovery of novel, low-molecular weight pharmaceuticals", In the Discovery of Natural Products with Therapeutic Potential (Ed. V.P. Gullo), Butterworth-Heinemann, London, UK. 49-80

- Frommel, M.I., Nowak, J. & Lazarovits, G., (1991), "Growth enhancement and developmental modifications of in vitro grown potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) as affected by a nonfluorescent *Pseudomonas sp.*", *Plant Physical*, **96**, 998-936
- Glick, B.R. & Penrose, D.M., (1998), "A model to the lowering of plant ethylene concentrations by plant growth promoting bacteria", *J. Theory Biol.*, **190**, 63-68
- Harayama, T. & Isono, K., (2002), "Sources of Microorganisms", *J. Microbiology*, **48**, 46-50
- Harbone, J.B., (1984), "Phytochemical Methods, A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis", Chapman and Hall, London
- Huang, W.Y., Cai, Y.Z., Xing, J., Corke, H. & Sung, M., (2007), "A potential antioxidant resource: endophytic fungi isolated from traditional Chinese medicinal plants", *Economic Botany*, **61**, 14-30
- Jacobson, C.B., Pastemak J.J. & Glick, B.R., (1994), "Partial purification and characterization of 1 aminocyclopropane-1-carbohydrate deaminase from the plant growth promoting rhizobacterium *Pseudomonas putida* GR 12-2", *Can. J. Microbial.*, **40**, 1019-1025
- Pelezar, M.J. & Chan, E.C.S., (1972), "Exercises in Microbiology", 3rd Ed., Mc Graw Hill Book Co., New York
- Petrini, O., (1986), Cambridge, UK, Cambridge University Press, 175-18
- Prescott, H., (2002), "Laboratory Exercise in Microbiology", 5th Ed.
- Saikkonen, K., Helander, M. & Faeth, S.H., (2004), "Fungal endophytes; hitchhikers of the green world; in plant microbiology" (eds).
- Salle, (1948), "Fundamental Principles of Bacteriology", Mc Graw Hill Book Co., Inc., New York
- Stahl, E., (1969), "Thin Layer Chromatography, A Laboratory Handbooks", George Allen and Unwin Ltd., London, Springer-Verlag Berlin, Heidelberg, New York
- Sullivan, D.J. & Gara, F., (1992), "Traits of fluorescent *Pseudomonas sp.* Involved in suppression of plant root pathogenus", *Microbial Rev.*, **56**, 669-676
- Stecher, G. P., (1968), "The Merck Index, An Encyclopaedia of Chemical and Drugs", Merck, Railway N.J., U.S.A.
- Vijava, P.L. & Mangala, D.S., (2011), "Fermentative production of L-glutamic acid GIS, Gitam University", *International Journal of Advanced Biotechnology and Research*, **2(3)**, 376-381